

ETHICS IN TEACHER-LEARNER RELATIONSHIPS IN UNIVERSITY SETTINGS IN BENIN

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ABSTRACT

"The relationships between teachers and learners are discussed either in terms of comprehensive justification or condemnation, but never in a neutral tone." This article aims to move beyond these registers to analyze the relationships between teachers and students in light of fundamental ethical principles accepted in the academic environment and to demonstrate that the learning crisis observed in universities is largely related to the poor management of these relationships.

The methodological approach, although socio-anthropological and oriented towards an ethnographic and comprehensive perspective of teaching practices, specifically the relationships between teachers and students, appears quite eclectic given the sensitivity of the research subject. It is coupled with a biographical approach focusing on the analysis of students and teachers' life stories, interview and focus group data, conversations and testimonies, as well as observational data.

From this research, it initially appears that the image, credibility, and prestige of the university institution in Benin seem to depend largely on the relationships between teachers and learners, which are often disconnected from the major ethical values and principles at play in higher education. This disconnection stems from, on the one hand, a lack of understanding of the purpose of education and, on the other hand, tensions between the values promoted by the university institution and the personal normative references of the teachers. Consequently, the prominence of the university system must rely on structural changes and profound transformations that current reforms have not yet managed to implement. Among these changes are the creation of new bodies to analyse ethical compliance by researchers, the establishment of new mechanisms or institutions to formalize the transmission of a unified basic cultural and pedagogical culture, which could serve as an "invisible mediator" or "invisible filter" in the absence of physical mediators within the university institution.

Keywords: Credibility, professional socialization, conflicting interests, learning crisis, Benin.

INTRODUCTION

Addressing the issue of ethics and relations between teachers and learners in the university setting as an academic is certainly not an easy task, because this results in analysing the practices of the actors interacting in a space that is not new to them. It is hardly an easy task in that it is a matter of reinventing the other in an exercise from which one cannot escape while it requires that one provides a great effort of objectivation, objectivity, and distancing, therefore not biased. This work beyond the question of the "teacher-learner" relationship that it addresses under the prism of

ethics in higher education will not stop to evoke not only the resonances with which the researcher negotiates in his research, but also the question of the other and of oneself both from an anthropological point of view as a subject and object of study, and ²from a moral perspective.

As a matter of fact, ethics is covered with several conceptions in many works, mostly philosophical. While for some, including Canivez (1988), ethics appears as morality that reminds us of the existence of duty and prohibitions, others, linking these duties and prohibitions and the normative referent specific to a community or a group, underline the relativity of morality and perceive it as the doctrine of action made available to humans, which invites us to judge ourselves, to monitor ourselves and to transform ourselves on behalf of respect for the rule. Such assertions link ethics to a vision, an intention that underlies the activity of a subject in act(s). This last conception refers in hollow to the existence of the OTHER, of its permanent balance between the other and me (Kant, 1997; Jankélévitch, 1998; Imbert, 1987).

In view of these different conceptions of ethics sometimes opposed to morality, sometimes perceived as the latter, I propose to inscribe myself here in a conception of ethics seen not exclusively as morality or intention, but in that of ethics at the confluence of collective ideals and normative and deontological referents. These are therefore the collective ideals that must structure the acts, practices and behaviours of university actors, on the one hand, the normative and deontological referents who must supervise their practices and acts and whose contravention would lead to the denial of the other, his rights and his needs of the freedom of the other, his vulnerability, human dignity, the prestige of the university institution and its functions, on the other hand.

Ethics and deontology, seen from this perspective, should frame any training, learning and education activities for life. The University is the place where the present is constantly negotiated and the figure of humanity is drawn. As such, public opinion expects all activities of the academic community to submit, globally and in full, to the rules and principles of ethics in general. As a result, the relationships between teachers and learners are evoked either in the register of fury or rage, or in that of condemnation with most often harsh judgments, but never in a neutral tone. This work aims to get out of this register to analyse the relationships between teachers and learners in the university in the light of fundamental ethical principles and to show that the current image and credibility of the university institution are largely the result of the management that is made of these relationships. We analyse excerpts from research results on this issue in the light of the fundamental ethical values that govern behaviours and practices within the academic institution.

1. Problem statement

The teacher-learner relationship, from elementary school to university, is characterized by a power relationship often seen as a relationship of authority (Napporn, 2016). The author is interested in the issue of authority in schools and the master-student relationship in Benin. She approaches it, basing on the observations made on the Beninese school system in terms of moral and sexual harassment, corruption and abuse of authority in various forms (cheating, sale and purchase of exam and competition tests, marketing of course supports and supervised work, etc.), the attitude of some parents seeking to defend their children versus teachers, the attitude of students who raise their hands on their teachers, etc. Her study was interested in secondary education. She revealed the premises of the crisis of the teacher's authority. In fact, in accordance with African culture, which makes age a criterion of value, the authority of the teacher was perceived, in Benin, as a natural extension of that of the parents until 1990. The adult always being right, the authority exercised by the teacher over the learner was rarely disputed (Gbaguidi, 2018). But in recent years, the new study programs at the primary and secondary levels in Benin, and the new higher education system called Bachelor, Master, Doctorate (LMD) have introduced new teaching practices and new relationships between teachers and learners, which practices show a break with the authoritarian relationships of yesteryear. Nowadays, teacher-learner relationships have become more complex and challenging in view of the effects they induce: performance declines for some, temporary or permanent dropouts or dropouts for others. Indeed, teacher-learner relationships when addressed in research, either directly or through other research, often focus on learner performance, or in research focusing on the issue of sexual or moral harassment. Some research work addresses this issue under its essentially pedagogical dimension in order to highlight the best pedagogical practices that can allow a good construction of knowledge by learners. When the issue of the teacher-learner relationship is addressed by Napporn (2016), it is much more from the point of view of relational quality, leadership and authority than it is. To this end, the author proposes that we are now much more concerned about the quality of the master-student relationship in Benin. According to her, "if most institutions and major reflections on education strongly insist on the qualification of teachers and the reevaluation of the teaching function, there is very little concern for the quality of the master-student relationship, which is nevertheless considered unsatisfactory by many actors in Benin (Napporn, 2016). She proposes that the question of authority no longer be evacuated from the educational relationship or the master-student relationship because, she explains, it is not necessary for it to be declined as in the past, that is to say in an authoritarian conception, which is no longer suitable. Today, in Benin, it is prescribed by the new study programs that students be co-authors and

actors in the construction of their knowledge. The authority of the master must therefore be thoughtful, limited and "of service": in one word, democratic (Gbaguidi, 2028).

Many other works emphasize the ethical dimension of the teacher-learner relationship. Many of these studies are interested in teacher-doctoral student relationships in higher education (Löfström and Pyhältö, 2017; Kurtz-Costes et al., 2006; Bruhn, 2008). Löfström and Pyhältö (2017) focus on the analysis of the concordance between the perceptions of supervisors and doctoral students regarding ethical problems in the natural and behavioural sciences. Kurtz-Costes et al. (2006) analysing the role of gender in the academic thesis writing experiences of doctoral students focus on doctoral programs, the supervisor-student relationship and the gender of the faculty and the advantages or disadvantages, in terms of performance, related to having female or male supervisors. Anderson and Louis (1994) by looking for the causes of inappropriate behaviour in the relationship between doctoral students and supervisors have been able to demonstrate that a gap between doctoral students and their work environment, in terms of difficulties with their supervisors and uncertain career prospects, contributes to ethical misconduct. Bruhn (2008), for his part, is interested in the explanatory reasons for inappropriate academic behaviour in higher education. He has shown that the breach of ethics in the academic world is not new, but its prevalence, its causes and the methods to prevent it are still the subject of debate. The author assumes that the dissonance of values is at the origin of most of the reasons why a breach of ethics occurs. It draws attention to the need for greater responsibility for the university institution, as a moral agency, in order to prevent the appearance of a breach of ethics.

Without claiming to be exhaustive in the mobilization of the scientific literature that addresses the issue, it still appears that the question of relations between teachers and students of various academic levels in higher education remains poorly documented. The question of ethics in teacher-student relations therefore appears as a fruitful empirical project to analyse the root causes of the crumbling of the image and prestige of the university institution on the one hand, and the inappropriate behaviour observed in universities in Benin, on the other hand.

In fact, the question of ethics in teacher-learner relationships has so far been part of the blind spots of research in higher education. Even if it tends to belong to the register of social phenomena that are both familiar and sensitive, the question of relations between teachers and learners, the vulnerability and the emerging dysfunctions and effects to which it exposes the different categories of university actors, paradoxically articulate with a rather tenuous knowledge of the social dynamics at work in these universes. Which universes are almost always approached

by the filter of preconceived ideas having, for real, nothing in common with reality. This sufficiently explains the interest of this work, which aims to describe and analyse the relationships between teachers and learners in their ethical dimension.

In recent years, this issue has become worrying both at the level of the university institution itself and at the level of the social body that houses it. In this sense, training is given to teachers (new and old) on university pedagogy and on the ethics and deontology of the teaching profession, the role of the teacher, the relations between teachers and learners, etc. in the West, in Africa, in general and Benin in particular. In fact, the African and Malagasy Council for Higher Education (CAMES) has integrated pedagogy as a criterion for evaluating teachers in order to ensure their pedagogical performance and allow them to better respect ethics and deontology in university settings.

In Benin, the social body, academics, learners and authorities at the top of the country are aware that respect for ethics is not a won bet. Aware of the discredit that such a situation generates on the education system, graduates and the scientific productions that come out of it, the Country has introduced reforms in higher education, including that relating to the sanitation of the sector. To this end, a National Control and Ethics Body (ONCE) is created, which will later take the name of Delegation of Control and Ethics (DCE). This delegation is set up to assess, beyond the academic aspect, the moral and ethical dimensions related to the behaviour of teachers in universities. Its mission is to evaluate higher education teachers with no distinction of grade or origin and the content of the courses. One of its prerogatives is to hear cases of violation of the deontological, professional, moral and ethical rules committed by Superior teachers and their collaborators, to rule on disciplinary matters, on the one hand, and to denounce to the Public Prosecutor cases of offences resulting from the behaviour of lecturers in the context of their teaching, supervision mission, in particular, harassment of all kinds, rape and corruption, exam fraud, on the other hand. Its mission is therefore to ensure that teachers and researchers respect higher education, professional obligations and ethics related to their status. Its mission is divided into three main poles of attribution, namely the control of the quality of education; the evaluation of lecturers and researchers and the control of respect for ethics and deontology. The DCE is in a participatory approach of co-construction with higher education stakeholders of the basics of a return to values. It aims to restore higher education's letter of nobility through a collective return to values so that the higher education teacher inspires confidence and forces respect to break with the crisis of confidence induced by the recurrence of unhonourable practices and acts of the actors of the university institution.

The ambition of the DCE is to have a university institution operating with reliable

standards and respected by all actors in the system. These standards are reinforced by reforms with a view to a more user-friendly and reassuring institution. However, the behaviours of the various stakeholders of this university institution that is the University are not in accordance with all these normative referents. The actors of the different university communities are for the most part aware that ethics is not always applied and that this state of affairs discredits the university institution. The most condemned actions that raise questions are those that take shape in teacher-student relations. The media (written and audiovisual press), social networks very often report cases of sexual or moral harassment in Beninese universities (public and private), cases of corruption (sale or orchestrated escape of tests), trafficking of notes and/or influence, confrontation, humiliation, psychological violence, etc. The recurrence of these facts compels the researcher to try to understand how the shortcomings and absences that have become structural in higher education are experienced and what are the effects on the relations between teachers and learners and on the image and credibility of the university institution in Benin?

The researcher maintains that the fundamental principles of ethics, which include the preservation of a climate of collaboration, the acceptance of differences and criticism in mutual respect, respect for the rights of others, the alignment of institutional values with personal normative references, and the absorption of structural gaps in higher education are essential to improve the relationship between teachers and students. This also promotes the improvement of the image of the academic institution, the return to fundamental values and the development of its community. At the basis of the present reflection, there are three lines of research:

- Ñ The University is a social arena that interacts a plurality of actors and involves a number of issues leading to differences in interests, views, perceptions and practices.
- Ñ Teacher-learner relationships are most of the time strongly influenced, on the one hand, by the objective structural characteristics of the university institution and its organization resulting from the crisis of States and Structural Adjustment Programs, and on the other hand, by the environment and professional socialization of the teacher.
- Ñ The image, credibility and prestige of the university institution in Benin seem to depend largely on the relations between teachers and learners, most often far from the major ethical values and principles at work in higher education, on the one hand, from the lack of knowledge of the meaning of education, the tensions between the values conveyed by the university institution and the normative staff referents of teachers, on the other hand.

2. Methodological approach: a research object between subjectivity and testing the neutrality of the researcher

The methodological approach adopted is of a socio-anthropological type based on the documentary research, the techniques of interview and direct observation. It is part of an understanding perspective.

The work is largely based on the stories and fragments of experiences of teachers, learners and parents of students. I opted for these stories and fragments of experiences because I am convinced that if for Jean Peneff, through the history of an individual, one can also make the history of institutions that are far from being clandestine (Peneff, 1990), the life stories of the actors on their experience seem equally important to understand the image of institutions and the relationship of these actors to norms and ethics. The analysis of these narratives has made it possible to open the debate on the problem of respect for ethical rules in the education system in general and more specifically in higher education as a central variable in the construction of the image of the university institution, but neglected in the practices of the actors.

This choice is all the more relevant as the major interest of a qualitative interview is that it not only provides factual information, but above all makes it possible to grasp the representations of the people interviewed, to grasp their vision of the world, that is to say the way in which they perceive and appropriate their social environment as well as their own place and their own role in this environment (Charlier and Campenhoudt, 2014). This approach has therefore made it possible to decipher the logics of the actors, their representations and to understand their practices and behaviours in the university environment and the meaning they give them. It has been of great use for this work since it is made of observations of concrete situations and the daily life of the actors, "chats" and all forms of exchange in a situation of prolonged interaction with the actors whose experience I am trying to identify and the logics underlying it.

This research object has a double peculiarity. The first is that it may *a priori* raise a problem of subjectivity to the extent that it is treated by a lecturer in her university environment that constitutes the environment of her research. The risk is great that one pours into value judgments for, the question of ethics is difficult to address without referring to morality and therefore without giving the impression of taking a position and inscribing oneself in a lesson giver posture. The question of respect for ethics is a collectively accepted rhetoric and no one can deny the importance of ethics or question the relevance of a reform about the respect for ethics, which presents itself as a project of hope, life and influence of the university institution, without

incurring institutional banishment. The obligation of scientific rigor based on distancing and triangulation is, in the present case, the only option for an anthropologist to put her feet in the daily dishes of an institution that employs her. Should I allow myself to be stuck by the guilt of having exposed the backyard facts of our universities and by the fear of them being discredited or should I describe the relationships in these learning spaces at the risk of them emptying or producing all forms of violence if nothing is done? The answer was prompt, as the obligation of neutrality, that is to say the exercise of empathy consisting of "joining" every actor in their experience, their emotions, their choices, regardless of the gender to which they belong, was imposed on me. To circumvent this potential bias of loss of subjectivity, I used an approach that allowed stakeholders themselves to define the problem and possible solutions that I tried to polish in the light of data triangulation and a solid analysis.

The second peculiarity is that this object has forced me to a rather eclectic technique that clearly breaks with data collection techniques, namely the technique of broken stick chats which is a time-intensive technique that can extend over several years as is the present case. The corpus of data that served as material in the writing of this work has been mobilized since 2013 and includes data on experiences lived by many lecturers, including me, as well as data from mobilized observations.

Given the delicacy of the subject, many interlocutors preferred to remain anonymous. To respect the word given, even the initials of their surname and first names will not be mentioned in the work. If the field investigation involves a large share of negotiation, it is also respect for commitments and the word given. It involves an unthought in terms of obligation that is nothing more than respect for the integrity of the interlocutors and even the actants of their discourses by the researcher.

The population of our survey is made up of lecturers, students, parents of students, especially since the ethical issue in the relations between lecturers and students cannot be analysed without these different categories of actors. I combined reasoned sampling and an iterative process (commonly called the "snowball technique") that consisted of adding new interlocutors over the course of the survey. I also used the terrain shift strategy advised by Hughes (J-E., Charlier, & L., Campenhoudt, 2017, p. 96) which in fact consists of "shifting one's gaze, accepting to be shaken in what we think we know a priori. Such an approach is a matter of taking into account an interactionist point of view according to which an individual, whoever he is, also builds himself at the heart of the interactions that link him to others. To understand him, apprehend his point of view and grasp his activities, it is relevant to understand how others perceive him, interact with him and condition his thinking and

activities". (J-E., Charlier, &L., Campenhoudt, 2017, p. 96). This strategy has therefore allowed me to give a voice to parents of students, temporary teachers, members of the administration.

Our method of data analysis is that of analysing the content of my interlocutors' discourses.

3. Presentation of the results

3.1. Objective structural characteristics of the university institution, Structural Adjustment Program (SAP), and massification of higher education and reality

In Benin, higher education takes place in four public universities and private ones in faculties, colleges and university institutes. Made of different durations according to the types of levels, the training generates graduates who can be listed in three categories, namely: graduates who have followed a « formation sélective à l'entrée¹» (écoles et instituts) "selective training at the entrance" (colleges and institutes), those who have followed a "non-selective training at the entrance" (the classic faculties with large numbers) and those who have combined the first two categories of training. In fact, the selection at the entrance to schools in Africa, in general, and in Benin, in particular, was like that made in France. The cream of youth was recovered to be formed for the benefit of republican interests. The Beninese higher education system continues to be part of a "statising" dynamic that leads it to develop in the direction of responding to the State's requests for agents or more in the sense of manufacturing aspirants to the "civil servant profession". The same idea already appeared in the early 1980s with Akindes (1981) who stated that in accordance with the provisions of Articles 33 and 35 of the National Education Orientation Act (Order 75-30 of 23 June 1975), the various training institutions have the mission of training the leaders of tomorrow in all scientific, technical and research sectors, by meeting the requirements of the Country in terms of development (Akindes, 1981).

Two types of skills were developed until the advent of the Bachelor's, Master's, Doctorate (LMD) system: the general ones of the classic faculties and the professional ones of schools and institutes. Before 1970, Benin trained its students in foreign universities, especially in Dakar, Abidjan and France (F. Akindes, 1981). According to the same author, the National University of Benin began its activities in 1970 with a

¹ We borrow the term "selective training at the entrance" from R. Delès (2018) who uses the expressions "selective training" and "few selective training at the entrance" to emphasize the fact that in certain trainings the recruitment of students is done on the basis of submitting a files in order to see the averages obtained at in certain disciplines, while in others (classic faculties) if there is a selection, it is not that rigorous.

number of 350 students. In 1976, the number of students at the National University of Benin already reached 2,102 students, an average annual increase of 37.97%. In 2011, the number of students tripled over the next ten years, from 31,299 students in 2000-2001 to 95,629 students in 2010-2011. These data show an average annual growth rate of 11.8%. In the absence of a flow regulation system, the pressure exerted by the lower levels is automatically passed on to the Superior who no longer has the means to offer quality education (Republic of Benin, 2013, pp. 27-28). A decade later, or 10 years later, the total number of students for the 2020-2021 academic year is 118,768 (including 91,129 students in public universities and 27,639 in private institutions) (2020-2021 statistical yearbook). This workforce in 2019-2020 was 122,270, a decrease of 2.95%. For this academic year, the share of students enrolled in the private sector is about 23.27% (Op. Cit.). The same source reveals a strong feminization of students with an upward growth in the gender parity index over the last five years from 0.58 to 0.77 for Private Higher Education Institutions (EPES) and from 0.40 to 0.49 for public universities between 2016-2017 and 2020-2021. However, there is a relative decrease in the number of female students in public universities (32.75%) compared with a relatively high presence of the latter in public universities (43.61%). In 2020-2021, foreigners represented 3.15% of the total number of registrants. While the proportion of foreign students in public universities was 1.7%, it is 7.93% in EPES.

The exponential increase in the number of students between 1970 (350 students), 1976 (2102 students), 2011 (95,629 students plus 51,195 students for the same year) and 2021 (91,129 students) is indicative of the existence of a craze that expresses both the policy of massification of higher education and an explosion in demand for higher education. An explosion that challenges the real capacity of the State (in terms of governance, resources and reception capacities of universities) to meet this demand.

The strategy of expanding education in many African and Asian countries has led to a significant increase in the number of students and graduates. This quantitative growth occurred without a proportional development of infrastructure, teaching staff and employment opportunities (Tama, 2019) especially in the contexts of the Structural Adjustment Program (SAP) that many States and therefore many universities experienced.

In fact, in recent years, African universities have been part of the dynamics of the LMD system. Both faculties and schools and institutes have embarked on the path of professionalization of training.

The reform of Benin's higher education that led to the adoption of the Bachelor, Master and Doctorate (LMD) system and which should have made it possible to

create bridges between university research and the job market (private sector) to achieve the training/ employment adequacy and reduce unemployment is experiencing difficulties in its implementation. This is followed by an exponential increase in unemployment that obscures the visibility and readability of the efforts made by universities. Indeed, this reform did not take into account the various constraints in financial, material and human resources to give higher education a chance to get out of the rut and to make universities real levers of industrial, technological, economic and social development. However, the current table of the structural characteristics of the higher education system reveals a mismatch between this reform imposed from above and the context in which it is implemented. This inadequacy leads to adaptations and adjustments that have a cost because of the requirements of vocational education. All these adjustments involve significant financial expenses. Vocational education is intrinsically incompatible with a massive expansion of teaching. In addition to traditional funding methods such as grants, registration fees and state funding, new approaches need to be considered. Indeed, the high demands in terms of practical work, tutored projects and internships increase the burden of teaching and administrative staff. In addition, the equipment used for practical work requires amortisation to allow its renewal, especially in the fields of information and communication technology where the costs of use are high due to the rapid obsolescence of the equipment. For stakeholders in the professional sector, remuneration rates must reflect the marginal utility of their work in the market. Finally, the number of rooms required for vocational training is generally higher than for equivalent general training (Brès, 2015).

This results in a university at a crossroads with regard to all the adaptations induced by the massification of education, the consequences of the implementation of the SAP on higher education, the requirements demanded by the implementation of the LMD system and reality. A reality that is nothing more than the crisis of the Jacobin State and universities revealing themselves through the difficult conditions of teaching and learning of learners as well as the working conditions of teacher-researchers.

3.2. From the crisis of the Jacobin State to the crisis of universities

In Benin, in the 1990s, while Education showed signs of weakness, political discourse was at "Education for All". Awareness sessions were held to increase the demand for education. It was therefore essential for the State to mobilize both human (teacher) and financial resources to meet these new challenges. But the reality is that civil servants, especially teachers, were the subject of a "symbolic stigma" that no longer made them essential actors to get out of the crisis tunnel. There was gradually a freeze on hiring. The weakening of the public service therefore freed up spaces

allowing new actors to break into the civil service scene. Many state sectors experienced staff shortages. But with renewed interest in Education, the Education sector was one of the sectors that most needed staff and investment to strengthen existing staff and infrastructure. But all this was without counting on the implications of the Structural Adjustment Program (SAP), namely the tacit taxation of the reduction of the number of civil servants and funding.

A detour through history allows me to identify two main causes of the shortage and diversification of teaching staff. On the one hand, in many African universities, we note the concern to honor the commitments related to the "universalization of Education" (for this, it was essential to strengthen the staff despite the closure of teacher training schools) and on the other hand, the budgetary restrictions that many African countries through the crisis of the 1980s had to observe. Thus, attempts to get the southern states out of the crisis (through SAP measures) had confined them in a situation of "delivery of public services without staff or without public service" to borrow the metaphor of Darbon (2001). Many African states, including Benin, have been forced to restructure their roles as providers of education and health services (Boidin and Savina, 1996). In the case of Benin, the objective was to reduce the share of personnel expenditure in current expenditure from 81% in 1990 to 70% in 1994. We witnessed the freezing of employment, the closure of teacher training schools and the enhancement of precarious jobs that only financially commit the State for a short period of time. In higher education, this has resulted in reduced recruitment and low state investment in infrastructure construction. The lack of recruitment results in the solicitation by universities and heads of entities of a large number of unrecruited doctors called "casual teachers". As for the low investment, it is expressed in terms of reduction of allowances (scholarships) and renovation of old buildings formerly occupied by public services or teacher training schools. In order to exist, some universities squat inadequate spaces densified in infrastructure. Laboratories, when they exist, lack funding and support to conduct cutting-edge research, produce knowledge and train resources necessary for the economic and social development of the nation. Everything suggests that this is a higher education which, in the absence of support, relegates scientific research to the background. Added to this is an almost non-existence of specialized libraries to facilitate both the updating of teaching and research. To these shortcomings and absences, is added the lack of well-equipped amphitheatres for classes, functional digital rooms and a good internet connection, laboratories and research centers, specialized libraries, the difficulty of access to the internet connection, despite the efforts of the Government, complicates the university community's access to recent documentation, participation in international scientific events and updating of teaching.

These ills resulting from the reduction of expenditure in the higher education system become more complex when we integrate the specificities of the institutions, some of which have to face very large numbers, for others the absence of a minimum of specialty equipment or application farms, etc. To all this is added the lack of working environment (offices for teachers, teachers' rooms) in some universities where teachers who do not wish to receive learners at home, are forced to take advantage of the shading of trees on the campuses to exchange in a rambling way with them.

Table 1: Number of students at public universities

University	Sex		Total	IP
	F	M		
UAC	22710	41976	64686	0,54
UP	6202	14484	20686	0,43
UNA	287	964	1251	0,30
UNSTIM	643	3863	4506	0,17
Total	29842	61287	91129	0,49

Source : DPAF/MESRS, 2023.

Table 2 : Registrations and number of students

Registration	Statut	Institutions	Sex		Total	IP
			F	M		
Students' Registration in the public	public universities	UAC	23482	43035	66517	0,55
		UP	6318	14675	20993 ²	0,43
		UNA	287	964	1251	0,30
		UNSTIM	643	3863	4506	0,17
Registration in the public			30730	62537	93267	0,49
Registration in the private			12053	15586	27639	0,77
Total registrations			42783	78123	120906	0,55
Number of students in the public			29842	61287	91129	0,49
Number of students in the private			12053	15586	27639	0,77
Total number of students			41895	76873	118768	0,54

Source : DPAF/MESRS, 2023.

The various recruitments organized for the benefit of universities have not yet made it possible to meet the enormous needs for teaching staff. This shortage of teachers limits the performance of both teachers and students. It is not superfluous to emphasize emphasis that higher education requires expertise and that in the face of this shortage, recruited teachers are forced to distribute the courses not performed, thus forcing themselves to leave their academic specialties. Thus, in 2021, the number of Higher Education teachers was 1184 without counting several hundred vacant teachers used according to the specificities of the entities. However, a need for 3000

² In 2024, l'UP has 25000 étudiants.

teachers is felt in the Public Universities of Benin (UPB).

Table 3 : Higher education teaching staff by body and sex

Bodies	Sex		Total	Women proportion (%)
	F	M		
Independent assistant teacher	2	9	11	18,2
Assistant	37	223	260	14,2
Assistant professor	59	345	404	14,6
Associate professor	49	278	327	15,0
Full professor	20	162	182	11,0
Total	167	1017	1184	14,1

Source : DPAF/MESRS, 2023

This table of higher education induces adaptations that are not without effect on the quality of the relationships between teacher-researchers and learners in Benin's universities. Faced with such a situation, higher education teachers function as if to say : since it is necessary to do against bad fortune a good heart, it is necessary to adopt strategies to bypass these constraints in the rather particular context that is theirs.

3.3. On the image, credibility and prestige of the university institution

3.3.1. Experience of social actors around structural constraints in higher education and ethical rules

If it happens to be true that the structural deficiencies revealed by the presentation of the table of public universities in Benin have led to strategies of either adaptation or circumvention among members of university communities (among other learners and teachers in their generality), it is also obvious that these strategies have generated underlying modes of operation in terms of practices and behaviours that good or bad participate in the construction of the image and prestige of the university institution.

In the following lines, perverse effects of cases of strategies for circumventing structural constraints will be presented and analysed in the light of a number of fundamental ethical and deontological values.

✓ On the seek for truth as an ethical value

Ethics in research is based on the principle of the search for truth. Indeed, the principle of the search for truth is based on a critical spirit stimulated by academic discussions concerning the knowledge produced and transmitted, as well as the perspectives and relevance of the sources used. Its credibility depends closely on

methodological rigor, ensuring results in accordance with the criteria of objectivity and impartiality. It also requires the integrity of the individuals involved both in the search for knowledge and in the interpretation of results. To achieve this goal, it is essential to present and balance all points of view, currents of thought and schools of thought, while allowing constructive and objective criticism. In addition, the search for truth implies the fair recognition of the contributions of all persons who have played a significant role in the design, realization of a research project, or in the content of the teaching.

Practices that go against this principle have gained momentum in recent years as it appears in the speech of a student enrolled in a master's degree at a public university:

"I was writing my research master's thesis with a teacher here. The latter asked to see the data I collected. I trusted him by sending him my work and my research data. I even went so far as to tell him about an article I was finalizing. He asked to see the article in order to give me his comments. A few weeks later, great were my amazement and disappointment to see the work on the net without informing me. For me, there is no worse form of wickedness and dishonesty than appropriating the work of a learner who has not even been financially helped in data collection, in our current context of lack of research grants. The most serious and inconceivable thing is that he positions himself as the first author of a work that does not even belong to him! I found it amazing. It is simply showing dishonesty and lack of dignity. (August 2023 interview with a Master's student from a university)

Sometimes, negotiations to be co-authors of works whose contents are totally unknown to teachers are legion among many candidates wishing to register on the aptitude lists of the Malagasy African Council for Higher Education (CAMES). A doctoral student explains:

"In my case, and the other master's and doctoral students will agree with me, I can say with no fear that the directors exploit us to have publications and pass their degrees at CAMES. Those who have to pass the competition to become Full Professor, go so far as to ask that they be positioned as first authors for work they have not even contributed financially to the data collection. My thesis supervisor demands that he always be positioned as the first author. See our workforce in the lab. If we all position him as the main author, see the number of articles for him without having contributed to anything! If at least he corrects the text for you, it's still acceptable! Most often, we even feel like we don't learn anything in the Laboratory. We are only good for their articles and the courses we prepare and provide them with. Sad reality of supervision in research laboratories". (Speaking with a doctoral student in 2024).

The quantitative requirement of publications to which candidates for the CAMES competition must respond and the implicit requirement of publication to which the perception of the publication bonus by the teacher is conditioned induce a cheat that does not say its name because it favours the strategy of "put my name on the article" or "give me an article to increase the number of my articles". The absence of a funding policy for university research makes this practice increasingly recurrent. This leads not only teacher-researchers to develop a manufacturing industry of

scientific productions, but also to break with the ethics of the search for truth.

Similar cases of misappropriation of the authorship of field data are legion in the Universities of Benin. Everything works as if this fraudulent practice were a teachers' strategy to circumvent not only the absence or insufficiency of laboratories but also the lack of funding for scientific research. While the quality of teaching is based on the renewal of the fundamental knowledge produced by research and the advancement of teachers is done by the light of well-made scientific publications and pedagogical activities, scientific research seems to be paradoxically relegated to the background, for lack of funding. In addition, scientific research seems to occupy a good place in the ranking of universities worldwide, while the conditions for serious structuring research are diminishing in African universities in general, and Beninese in particular. The question remains as to the relevance and possibility of the principle of truth in a context of economic constraints.

Many research funding organizations and academic institutions recognize that research collaborations between regions make it possible to target studies more effectively and increase their quality (Bucher *et al.*, 2020). In the same logic, Oswald *et al.* (2016), suggest that, in committed research, excellence is based on four pillars: quality, impact, partnerships and co-construction. The university institutions of Benin are part of the same dynamic by admitting that the production of data in a university environment could and should be done in partnership by a team of teacher-researchers and learners, either in the context of research to lead to the writing of bachelor's, master's dissertations or theses, or in the context of multidisciplinary research. The teacher-researchers enrolled in this partnership approach differ from each other by their practices, for some in phase, for others in total break with ethics.

In the first case, teacher-researchers mobilize the data collected by their learners to make collective publications bearing both the names of the learners who participated in the data collection and their own names, as evidenced in this interview excerpt:

"In the absence of adequate funding for research, it is essential to develop effective strategies for publishing articles. In our team, we rigorously supervise the collection of field data for the theses of our master's students, in order to use this data for publications. Students do most of the work, while we intervene to improve and complete the work before publishing it, often assigning the first place in the list of authors to the main student. This approach, common among our colleagues, helps to reach the number of articles necessary for applications to the CAMES aptitude lists". (Chat with a group of research teachers from a UP entity).

This principle of searching for truth requires the teacher-researcher, according to the code of deontology and ethics of the teaching staff at university level in Benin, the probity particularly since he must exercise his functions with honesty, academic and

scientific integrity, righteousness, attachment and without greed. He must respect intellectual property. It is forbidden to him among other things for example, according to this code:

To direct the research work of students to his personal advantage; to use university or research funds for personal purposes; to divert to his benefit or to that of third parties confidential information or research results to which they have access in the exercise or on the occasion of the exercise of his duties at the University (...) The teacher or researcher is prohibited from reproducing in his research work excerpts from the work of other authors without explicitly indicating the source. He is obliged to respect the intellectual property of others. He avoids appropriating the work done by other researchers. The teacher or researcher is prohibited from any falsification of a document or research result. He is required to provide accurate information about his work (DCE, 2024)

The crumbling of the prestige of the teacher-researcher and by ricochet of the university institution, observed in recent years, is somewhat explained by the non-observant practices and "actions" around scientific publications. These actions and practices also raise ethical problems of academic freedom and respect for the person as can be seen in the following lines.

3.3.2. Tension between the values conveyed by the university institution and the teachers' personal normative referents

In a context of lack of institutions that can supervise behavioural drifts, the academic community becomes the theatre of abuse and abuse of power, including sexual and moral harassment of students by teachers. These practices, combined with failed grade management systems and unofficial financial requirements for academic supervision, reveal a poisonous institutional culture that compromises students' right to a safe and respectful academic environment. These practices break with the principle of academic freedom and respect for the person when cases of student rape become frequent in offices or hotel rooms serving as workspaces, for lack of an office, or when the University is transformed into a factory space of false fees that the student must pay for activities normally covered by the State in the salary of teachers.

The University ultimately appears as a space of practices in which the practices of the actors do not match with academic freedom and respect for people. Two fundamental ethical principles are constantly flouted by some teachers.

3.3.3. On the principles of academic freedom and respect for the person

In fact, academic freedom must be exercised in compliance with the laws, university obligations and ethical standards. It includes the freedom to choose the subjects of teaching and research and protects against the censorship of critical opinions, as long

as the rights of others are respected. This freedom is linked to the independence and integrity of individuals, with an obligation of transparency regarding favours, gifts and financing. Conflicts of interest must be declared, and personal influences must not interfere with academic functions. Finally, external activities must be conducted with loyalty to the institution, and teachers must focus on their responsibilities for which they are paid. Many of these teachers are in the consultancy, abandoning their academic positions to their doctoral students or assistants whom they do not pay or who are paid if necessary, with the resources of the Country.

Academic freedom formally prohibits the use of influence associated with a function for personal purposes or to favour family members and relatives. It also requires members of the university community to reject the practice of continuously assisted favourites within the system, which has unfortunately become common and generates various trafficking and unorthodox practices aimed at ensuring the effortless success of the privileged (trafficking of notes, complaints followed by negotiations, harassing intervention with colleagues, etc.).

"I am a professional in one of the decentralized services of the State. I am passionate about discipline X. For this I decided to engage on the adventure of learning this discipline. This will also and above all be of great importance to me in the exercise of my profession especially since I am close to retirement, I told myself. But given the burdens of my profession, I could not validate all the Teaching Units. This is how I had four Teaching Units (UE) left to validate. Teachers therefore promised to help me, but in return I had to make certain facilities for them in the delivery of state service in my sector. What I did. But I didn't win the case in return. In my presence, the UE grades were modified in order to allow me to go to the next year, but to my surprise, at the start of the school year, when I wanted to withdraw my validation certificate from the past semester, I found that I still owed the same Teaching Units. When I approached one of them, he let me know that they had unfortunately forgotten to record the changes they had made to my notes. That's what I've been through." (Excerpt from a chat with a state agent registered in a university).

Such degrading and disabling practices sometimes aim to make deserving learners fail as one can note it in the words of this teacher who witnesses a practice of abuse of power.

This story goes back to several years behind me, but I was marked negatively and indelibly as you mark an animal as an identification. It's a story that happened in 2014. What is it about? I started by supervising a student in the writing of his bachelor's thesis. This student was one of the best students of his class. We were at work when the student in question informed me that the administration had changed his supervisor. And it's up to me to ask him if he didn't inform the administration that he had already started working with another teacher? The latter reassured me that he had done it. I was challenged by one of the teacher colleagues who were older than me. It is up to one of them to express himself in these terms: "we know that it is you who supervises him and that is precisely why we have replaced you with another colleague who is often absent. If you supervise him, he will do a very good job and it could raise his head to the point of wanting to continue his studies to later become a colleague of ours! He must understand that we suffered before being here. Don't take him personally, but we want to teach him respect and humility. When I approached this student, he told me that one of the teachers

who had questioned me was making advances to a girl who is in the same study group as him and quite close to him. Having seen them several times, even during break hours, the teachers would have had ideas and this has poisoned the relationship he had with him. This student was embarrassed to no longer know how to be accepted by his teachers. I had to tell the student not to care and that we would do the following thing: he meets his new supervisor in order to work together every time the teacher came for his teachings since the latter did not live in the University environment. At the same time, I continue to work with him, that we would pretend not to work together anymore and that he should not thank me on the thank you page. This is how we worked and the two supervisions he benefited from without anyone realizing it allowed him to do a very good job with a very good mention, the best mention of his promotion by the way" (Interview with a university teacher).

It is right that Article 19 of the Code of Deontology and Ethics for Higher Education Teaching Staff in Benin provides that:

" The teacher or researcher is required to properly and effectively fulfil his obligations while demonstrating rigor, fairness, loyalty, civic spirit and courtesy in the performance of his duties in particular in his relations, both with his superiors, colleagues and subordinates and with learners and other users of the University or the research centre" (DCE, 2024).

As for the principle of respect for the person linked in one way or another to that of academic freedom, it is fundamental to ensure the safety and well-being of members of the academic community. It begins with the elimination of all forms of violence, whether physical, psychological, moral or sexual. This includes, in particular, the prohibition of any negative discrimination based on social, religious, ethnic, sexual, and other criteria, both in the fulfilment of teaching and research missions and in interactions within the academic community. At the same time, positive discrimination is being considered to offer special support to people in vulnerable situations. Respect for the person also requires the total eradication of any form of harassment, whether psychological, moral, sexual, or other.

In summary, respect for the person within the university implies zero tolerance for violence, negative discrimination, and harassment, while promoting a culture of inclusion and support for vulnerable individuals. In recent years, many voices have been raised to vigorously denounce the scourge of harassment, calling for its final resolution. Sanctions are now in place and are applied against those who violate these rules.

This problem highlights the nature of the relationships between teachers and learners, which manifest themselves in various ways. For example, some teachers engage in an odious blackmail by threatening students with bad grades if they do not accept their sexual advances. Some refer to this practice by the expression "red pen blackmail". This practice not only demotivates but also violates the fundamental rights of women and men to unhindered education.

This is why respect for the other must not be linked to the assignments, attributions or hierarchical situations of the person. The organization and conduct of the examinations must ensure fair treatment for students, based on the criteria of objectivity and impartiality. This principle of respect for the person requires the preservation of the confidentiality of the personal data of the various members of the community. The principle of respect for the person as well as Article 21 on the obligation of dignity or honourability (SGFP, art. 26 para. 1) of the same code stipulates that:

"The teacher or researcher is a social model. As such, in and out of service, it avoids any conduct that may compromise the dignity or honour of its functions or of the institution to which it is attached. He is wary of any misconduct harmful to the image of this institution, including alcoholism and gender-based violence, especially moral or sexual harassment against learners, persons subject to his supervision or those with whom he is in contact in the exercise or on the occasion of the exercise of his duties" (DCE, 2024: page?).

Cases of harassment, trafficking in notes, rape and persecution are legion and at the basis of academic dropout and disaffection with the academic thing in the rank of many young people most often women. The result is an unfriendly learning environment, bringing violence of all forms for learners and affecting the image of the university institution. Indeed, the university is a social arena that interacts a plurality of actors and brings into play a number of issues leading to differences in interests, points of view, perceptions and practices that are sometimes not very conciliatory.

For many parents of students, divided between the desire to see their children continue their studies and the fear of the risk of harassment and persecution incurred by the latter, the University far from being a high place of knowledge is rather an unsafe space for their children as it emerges in a chat between a teacher and a student's mother:

"I was traveling on the same bus as a student's mother with whom I found myself side by side. During the trip, we sympathized and talking about everything and nothing, she having understood that I was teaching at the University, exclaimed: "tell me, how is it going with the girls in your university? My daughter who is enrolled in your university came home one evening crying and told me this": "mom get me out of this place: we girls, our sex will "finish" [wear out (Translation TC)] at the pace where things are going and given the way our teachers use us to make their colleagues have a good time when they come on a teaching mission. We are sent to them in turn and the most difficult thing is that we know each other, we, the girls sent to them. When you try to refuse, they change your grades and you see that you only have lousy grades even in the subjects in which you thought you had worked. The most painful thing is when you work in a subject, so you know you're done with it and following your refusal, they post a new grade in the end-of-year results and let you know that it was a mistake. Mom, get me out of here, I beg you." Are there things like that in your university? She asked me. I listened to her ashamed, when she added: "For two years, my daughter has been at home doing nothing". The shame that took over me increased and I felt obliged to help the student

resume classes. I promised to stop by to see them at their home. Something I did. I helped the girl the following school year to have a registration in another entity through the University Orientation Committee (CUO) system and she was accepted and was supposed to resume classes in this new entity. According to the latest news, the latter left the University, was married and gave birth last year. Disaffection, disappointment, indignation or helplessness against a harassing and powerful system? Only this former student can say it." (Excerpt from a chat with a student mother in 2018).

In the eyes of parents, the perception of the University is changing, revealing a lack of congruence with its primary vocation, which is to teach, to instil the ethics of research and to educate and to prepare for working life. Such a perception is more constructed by parents living in rural areas. To this cognitive dissonance (Festinger, 1957) experienced by parents because of this incongruity between the reality of the university institution that welcomes their children and their expectations, is added the hardly acceptable unemployment of public university products. This incongruity gives the impression of witnessing the fabric of university "deinstitutionalization".

As a result, the image, credibility and prestige of the university institution in Benin seem to depend largely on the relations between teachers and learners, most often far from the major ethical values and principles at work in higher education, on the one hand, the lack of knowledge of the meaning of education, the tensions between the values conveyed by the university institution and the personal normative referents of teachers, on the other hand. In addition, the analysis of the interlocutors' speeches made it possible to understand the existence of a gap between the perceptions and expectations of social actors vis-à-vis the teacher and the image that the latter's non-observant practices refer to the social body in which he moves. It follows from the perceptions of members of the university community and social actors in general that the role of the teacher goes beyond instruction, the inculcation of knowledge or the teaching of a subject. For them, teaching means inspiring their learners the confidence necessary to follow the teacher, finding in him benchmarks for their daily and future life that they will lead outside the walls of the amphitheatres. Teaching means, for a teacher, making his actions say how much he feels responsible for the success and even the failures of his learners. To the question of what meaning to give to education, a seductive answer given by H. Arendt forces us to think that the relations between teachers and teachers described in the excerpts of interviews mentioned, place some teacher-researchers in Benin in a dynamic contrary to the meaning given by H. Arendt to education. Indeed, according to her, education is a birth that he explains in these terms:

"The teacher bears the responsibility of the world": to respond to a sensible world". The teacher says: "here is our world". In this sense, education is indeed a birthplace. So when we teach, we don't have the right to think badly of this world! For this world to be shared, it must make sense. (...) learning is underpinned by an act of faith (...) There is no possible complicity with the absurd. Whatever the discipline taught, the teacher is the man of responsible speech, who submits himself first to the requirements of a mastered,

fair, elegant language. He who speaks first submits to the demands of the rule, to the demands of truth. No one can cheat with language and its requirements (...) Language, in fact, carries within it the first and essential discipline, the mastery of violence, vulgarity, the requirement to submit oneself to the rules that one teaches. Fleeing from impropriety, not contradicting ourselves, being understood, responding, language gives us our first and most essential responsibilities". (Barrage et al., 2016, pp. 54-55)

It is obvious that the role of the teacher is lengthening and updating over time. Some will say of the teacher that he is both an expert, coach and evaluator (Koutinhoun et al., 2011), to notify his ubiquity in the school / academic dimensions and in the private life of the learner. As such, the relationship between the teacher and his learner should bear the signs of responsibility, with regard to the sense of education and the role of the teacher. A role that goes far beyond teaching, because "teaching is also educating, it is at the same time educating" (Grand, 2016). Such a role requires the commitment and responsibility of the teacher.

3.3.4. On the principle of responsibility

Numerous studies have shown the importance of the Pygmalion effect in learning, that is, the tendency of an individual's performance to improve according to the level of confidence and expectation that a parent, teacher or coach has towards his success. There is less and less production of such effects by teaching practices in universities that are accused of putting unemployed people on the job market. While the teacher's responsibility is to produce a positive effect on the skills development process of his learners, some teachers produce a Golem effect through their practices. The Golem effect is a psychological phenomenon implementing a self-fulfilling prophecy in which lower expectations placed on an individual lead him to poorer performance. This effect, which illustrates how a negative assessment of potential by a parent, teacher or any other authority figure can lead to less satisfactory performance, is also another cause of academic loss in universities. A learner explains:

" I was enrolled in an entity of a university. If I found myself elsewhere today it is because I understood that the teachers we had in my sector could only push me towards failure. When some of them come to classes, not only did they spend their time talking to us about themselves, their exploits, the time of their schooling, or their university studies, or when they flirted with women, they also demotivated us. How can you understand that a teacher says in the middle of class that it is difficult to have the average in his subject and that we who are in front of him are only future zémidjan men (motorcycle taxi drivers)? I realized that I had nothing good to hope for in such training and that I had to scrutinize other horizons to find a good sector where I would be motivated" (Speech of a learner, August 2022 in Parakou).

Such a discourse reveals a problem of lack of pedagogical competence and non-institutionalization of professional socialization, the result of which produces

"What I tell you here goes back several years. One of our teachers who was very feared by his wickedness and lack of benevolence had asked us to make a presentation on a text he published. Knowing that in the library of our university, it was not possible to find

more than one copy of this text, it preceded us to go and remove from the shelves of the library the only copy that was there! (...) One of our classmates was lucky enough to have the article thanks to a teacher who in turn borrowed it from our teacher. But the latter attacked the teacher who provided us with the article so that we could photocopy it. How can we be a teacher and create difficulties for learners when he is supposed to be a facilitator for us! Either it was due to wickedness, or to the old pedagogy, otherwise I still don't understand this attitude." (Interview with a former student who became a teacher-researcher).

These two narratives pose the problem of the quality of relations between teachers and learners. The first story reveals both the problem of lack of pedagogical competence and professional socialization, in addition to this problem, the second story poses the problem of lack of library documentation and professional socialization. Even the stories of the trafficking of notes, influence and harassment pose, with some exception, the problem of professional socialization.

Indeed, many teachers have internalized the fact that the teacher's prestige is built by his inaccessibility due to fear of his person, the difficulty his learners experience in working well when evaluating his teachings and the difficulty in understanding his teachings. Many teachers assisted teachers who had this perception of the teacher and the relationship that the teacher should have with his learners. Having therefore been « seduced » by this representation around teaching, teachers have internalized this way of being and doing that breaks with the requirements of the teaching profession and the ethical principle of responsibility that should define it.

Their perception of teaching is certainly due to the old pedagogy, in general, to the non-mastery of university pedagogy and to the fact that they have probably seen few other ways of doing things that compell them to teach simply as they were taught. This strongly decried perception of teaching and the teacher contributes to the degrading construction of the teacher's role and to that of the image of the university institution, which ultimately appears as an institution that only draws its prestige from the failure of learners. The teaching practices internalized by some no less numerous teachers, strongly influenced by the environment in which they have « learned the profession of higher education teacher » structure the relationships between them and their learners. The observation of these practices and the analysis of the discourses of the latter make it possible to affirm that teacher-learner relations are most of the time strongly influenced, on the one hand, by the objective structural characteristics of the university institution and its organization resulting from the crisis of the States and the Structural Adjustment Programs, and on the other hand, by the environment and professional socialization of the teacher.

Each member of the university is bound by the principle of responsibility to contribute to the scientific and cultural influence of the community, to strive for excellence and quality, to accept constructive criticism and to recognize the

importance of inter-disciplinary collaboration. A teacher who considers that the skills to be developed by the learner at the end of his teaching complement those of another course, will hardly venture to hide books or the bibliography of his course from his learners, let alone denigrate the teachings of his peers. This principle establishes that the institution and its members must be aware of the impact of their actions on students and the university community, and be able to be accountable in this regard. It also ensures that the institution protects the autonomy and personal integrity of its members, protecting them against any disclosure of data that could harm them. The preservation of the personal integrity of learners presupposes, for example, that we respect them and avoids the demobilization of the latter by behaviours that can produce a Golem effect on them. The principle of responsibility states that, within the university community, the university's priority is to ensure the quality of the training provided to students using the most appropriate teaching methods. It requires university teachers to share their knowledge with as many people as possible, as long as it does not directly affect their research. As far as possible, they must make the content of their teachings fully accessible to the scientific community. As such, the teacher is required to give learners all these sources of information, as well as the standard answers to the tests and exercises he gives as part of the evaluation of his teachings. This principle also stipulates that the teaching provided, the curricula and their contents, as well as the research, must be subject to continuous evaluation to ensure compliance with the standards and procedures governing the functioning of the institution. As a result, the teacher is also evaluated as much as the learner because the University must be able to guarantee the knowledge taught to learners and assess its relevance or danger to the learner or the society.

The question of the preservation of personal integrity of members of the scientific community, the preservation of their image and that of the academic and academic institution is addressed by the code of deontology and ethics of higher education teaching staff in its article 26 containing "obligation of consideration towards other members of the scientific community" and stipulates that the teacher or researcher must show respect and courtesy towards all the people with whom he interacts in the course of his duties. He is obliged to avoid any contemptuous, abusive or humiliating behaviour towards them. In addition, it must maintain healthy interpersonal relationships with other members of the academic or scientific community, thus promoting collaboration and strengthening a positive image of the academic institution (Excerpt from the code of deontology and ethics of higher education in the Republic of Benin). This article provides that the teacher respects several obligations (contained in this article) in the exercise of his freedom of judgment and critical analysis.

4. Discussion

In this research, it was a question of seeking to understand "how the shortcomings and absences that have become structural in higher education are experienced and what effects are on the relations between teachers and learners and on the current image, credibility and prestige of the university institution in Benin. The analysis of observation data and discursive data (individual interviews, discussions, exchanges of experiences and testimonies) allowed us to argue that the fundamental principles of ethics, which include the preservation of a climate of collaboration, the acceptance of differences and criticisms in mutual respect, respect for the rights of others, the alignment of personal normative references with institutional values and the resorption of gaps that have become structural in higher education are essential to improve the relations between teachers and students. This also promotes the improvement of the image of the academic institution, the return to core values and the development of its community

4.1. From the massification of higher education to the massification of teachers: the need for profound changes

I have highlighted the gaps that have become structural such as the lack of funding for research, documentary resources and adequate laboratories that hinder the functioning of higher education, on the one hand, and the circumvention strategies adopted by teacher-researchers, on the other hand. These strategies include the misappropriation of research data by teachers for their personal benefit, illustrated by cases where student dissertations or articles are used without proper recognition, or even fraudulently attributed to others. If these strategies compromise the credibility of scientific publications and betray students' trust in their supervisors while vitiating their relationships, they just as much destroy the image of the University. If the massification of education has taken place at all levels of education in a context that still bears the marks of Structural Adjustment Programs and the economic crisis that the world is going through, this massification has also led to an exponential increase in the number of students and teacher-researchers. This increase in their workforce leads to financial difficulties that make it difficult to operate the laboratories, carry out advanced research and update physical and digital documentary resources. As a result, the influence of the university system must be based on both structural and profound changes that the reforms undertaken have not yet been able to put in place.

These changes should concern the financing of universities and the reorganization of the evaluation of research carried out by teachers; the structuring of the system of appreciation of publications with the creation of new bodies for the analysis of

compliance with ethics by researchers, the establishment of a system of valorisation of university research conducted by teachers and their learners. To compensate for the lack of documentary resources, we could consider the financing of digital libraries, the subscription to digitized documentary collections and the establishment of a system for putting publications online by the University Scientific Councils.

Alarming cases of abuse and abuse of power, including sexual and moral harassment of students by teachers, were exposed. These abusive practices, coupled with poor transcript systems and unofficial financial requirements for academic supervision, reveal a dissident professional culture. That which, while revealing a misalignment between the institutional and personal standards and values of teachers, deprives students of their right to a safe and respectful academic environment. If this normative dissent reveals the existence of values that compete with those required in higher education, it is characteristic of a heterogeneity of the profiles of the group of higher education teachers and therefore of a diversity of values and normative references underlying the behaviours and practices of the latter. This normative pluralism that underlies behaviours and practices reveals a professional group of teachers who incorporate cleavages that are only perceptible in the observation or analysis of their "actions". This diversity of references observed in the ranks of teachers transforms the university institution into an arena where ardent university leaders who defend ethics and institutional values oppose and rub shoulders, conformist teachers who adhere to the norms and texts of laws in force in higher education, teachers whose practices and behaviours reveal the incorporation, into the institutional framework, of internalized norms from their professional socialization. This results into a division among teachers between those who are in line with the values of the university institution and those whose personal values do not align with institutional ones.

Indeed, higher education is the level of education where the initial training of teachers has never been organized before the entry into the function of the latter. Everything works as if the title of doctor were a guarantee of pedagogical and ethical skills. In fact, with the closure of schools for teacher training at the maternal, primary and secondary levels under the implementation of SAP, higher education has opted for learning the style of "*learning by doing*" and "*observational learning*" of Albert Bandura's theory of social learning. According to the latter, the majority of social learning is done on a vicarious basis by observing the behaviour of others and the consequences that result for them (A. Bandura, 1963). The theory of social learning is based on the vicariant effect, where the observation of models influences the learning process. The conception of professional socialization in higher education suggests that learning the teaching profession is based on the principle of Bandura's social

learning. The observation of the practices of thesis supervisors considered a priori as mentors or models would not only be enough to learn the ropes of the trade quite quickly, but would also allow the State to make savings; the challenge being much more the reduction of State burdens with regard to SAP. Thus, many higher education teachers reproduce what they saw their thesis supervisor do with just a few small differences in the « reconstruction » that the latter have made of the symbols and models retained from their observations; which reconstruction refers to the concept of « human agency » of Bandura (1963) which underlines the role of the subject's own action in any so-called vicariant learning process. As a result, the learning of the profession of university teacher on a vicariate basis integrates elements related to the reconstruction of the actor in a learning situation, i.e. the future teacher (doctoral student). But the observation of these « teaching apprentices » once in the role of teacher reveals a mixture of achievements of vicariant learning and elements of their personal reconstruction that bears the mark of both their academic and cultural environments. This idea emerges in the analyses of Bandura (1963) and Bruner (1991) even if the targets are not the same.

In the context of higher education where the group of teachers is a heterogeneous group with fragmented profiles, with a diversity of normative referents, it follows that each teacher has his system of values and professional norms built on the basis of the acquired knowledge (in phase or not with ethics) of vicariant learning, the culture of the professional environment and his own culture made of all the norms and values resulting from his education. When in his vicariant apprenticeship, the apprentice-teacher worked alongside a teacher whose professional culture had incorporated non-observant practices and behaviours that were not aligned with those of the university institution, the result was a new teacher strongly influenced by that figure of his initial learning. But when the professional culture of the « master » is in phase with ethics, that is to say the culture of the university institution, then, balance or the opposite is played at the level of personal norms and values built on the basis of his education. It is at this level that the basic education of each actor becomes essential in the analysis of the relationships between teachers and learners.

In fact, the question of formalizing the professional socialization of teachers going beyond the framework of simple training in university pedagogy (as is done in public universities) and that of co-education will have to be integrated into the higher education system. The heterogeneity of teacher profiles brings me back to the evidence of the non-existence of a common basic institutional culture yet necessary that the system must create. It can only be done through the creation of new devices or new institutions that formalize the transmission of a common basic culture

through professional socialization.

This professional socialization is all the more essential as it can transmit a unified basic institutional culture that can play the role of "invisible mediation" or "invisible filter" in the absence of real mediators within the university institution. The construction of this cultural and institutional knowledge serving as an invisible filter or mediator to each teacher will be the responsibility of the competent authorities, but will have to result from a framework for the co-construction of the new standards to structure the interactions between members of the university community in general and between teachers and learners in particular. This lack of common institutional culture is illustrated by narcissistic, demotivating, even humiliating behaviours observed among teachers, towards students is indeed one of the major dysfunctions that undermine the quality of education and compromise the relations between teachers and students. This institutional culture, which serves as the basis for the socialization of members of the university community, could help improve behaviours.

4.2. On the institutionalization of education, evaluation and control of ethics

The text also raised the question of academic freedom, often compromised by practices of indirect censorship and favouritism, where critical opinions are repressed in favour of personal relationships or personal gains of teachers. This seriously harms intellectual integrity, the diversity of ideas within academic institutions and the promotion of excellence. If the creation of this common basic culture prepares for different forms of bipolarity (failure / success / poor performance / good performance, adequate development of performance and its opposite, unemployment / employability, life / death, etc.) it will predispose the actors to a positive perception of failure without seeking to negotiate results that we do not deserve. Such behaviours raise the problem of the absence of instances that can play a key role in the higher education assessment system. The role of these bodies is to reframe the interactions between the professional role of the teacher and the learners as far as I am concerned in this text.

Parsons' view on the medical role and its interaction with the patient client could very well be transposed to the teacher-learner relationship. In fact, the role of teacher, like any professional role, should be exercised in an interaction with the role of the learner, user of the « professional », who is both dependent on the teacher by his unconditional desire to train and autonomous because of the limited scope of the teacher's competence and his independence from any hierarchical and public supervision (code of deontology and ethics of higher education teaching staff). If the teacher is « obliged » to train his learner, the learner will have to open up to his

teacher, share with him all his doubts, his needs for clarification and clarification of knowledge in the field of his expertise: this reciprocal obligation should create the possibility of institutionalization of the exchange and therefore the professionalization of the role of teacher through institutions of training, learning, listening, education, ethical control of professional practice (teaching, evaluation and content of teaching. Such institutions will help restore trust, strengthen academic independence and promote a culture of transparency and responsibility within higher education institutions, on the one hand, and better reframe the relationships between teachers and learners, on the other hand.

Speaking of an institution of Education, the University should integrate the « Education » dimension to find the « missing link » of its optimal functioning, namely informal education through the inculcation of educational values by the parents of students and the University. The University has always functioned without this important link under the pretext that adult students of adult age do not come to the University, forgetting that the massification of education and the New Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) have implicitly renewed the profiles of learners welcomed by the University. Among these new profiles is a category of immature learners, left to themselves who are looking for themselves in a universe that is difficult to identify. For this, instituting informal education in the higher education system why not higher education proves to be ultimate in order to make them actors of this inevitable « co-education » (Op. Cit.). We know that socialization has no age and should continue at every stage of life. This idea emerges in Berger and Luckmann (1966) when they formulated the hypothesis that « socialization is never totally successful » (p. 146) and socialization is never total or finished » (p. 188). « It is therefore necessary to give an important place to secondary socialization provisionally defined as « internalization of specialized institutional subworlds » and acquisition of specific knowledge and roles directly or indirectly rooted in the division of labour » (p. 189). This is, above all, the incorporation of specialized knowledge (which we will call professional knowledge) that constitutes knowledge of a new kind (Berger and Luckmann, 1966). Knowledge of a new kind that should incorporate the basic educational values that Berger and Luckmann (1966) designate by the concept of « basic knowledge of primary socialization ». Such values will help the actors of the university community to know how to better manage both structural gaps and frustrations and forms of violence.

The lack of pedagogical competence among some teachers, illustrated by narcissistic, demotivating or even humiliating behaviours towards students, which is one of the major dysfunctions that undermine the quality of education and compromise the relationships between teachers and students, could be managed by this formal

professional socialization (or « professional knowledge ») incorporating « basic educational values » to be institutionalized in the university system. It does not matter the term by which this type of value is designated. The essential thing is that it refers to values and knowledge that must improve relations among actors and facilitate living together within the university institution and which no educational system can ignore without disappointment. The same idea emerges in Faurroux (1996) who evokes the issues of the common bases that he refers to as « primordial knowledge ». He affirms « that there are, knowledge that, for lack of being acquired in time, is lost forever and that are those that have universal value, of daily use, of constant need, that allow one to fit into a group, in vocational training, in a job, to help usefully one's fellow man, to overcome frustration without resorting to violence ». For him, this essential knowledge is imposed on any educational system (Chudeau, 2021). These two types of professional and citizen socializations will make it possible to revisit the functions of the university institution. Finally, the issue of massification in a context of SAP implementation that has led to gaps that have become structural in terms of lack of adequate lecturers, teachers, appropriate teaching materials and complexity of the evaluation system, thus weakening the completion rate of university studies added to the effects of the global crisis that does not spare students' parents, could use resilience strategies related to the online publication of courses and online evaluation. But this implies a political will and investment, both from the State and from families, to the extent of this ambition. Such a reform on digital university pedagogy has many implications in terms of teacher training, construction of appropriate infrastructures, etc. It aspires to be an open door to knowledge, free from time and space constraints. From this perspective, it acts as a technical tool facilitating access to training for various audiences, regardless of their context or constraints. In addition, it encourages pedagogical innovation by allowing, by its very nature, a redefinition of the relationship between teachers and learners or even its improvement.

CONCLUSION

University is a social arena that interacts a plurality of actors and involves issues leading to differences in interests, points of view, perceptions and practices. The analysis of teacher-learner relationships reveals a disarticulation between the individual and others; a disarticulation or rupture that refers to the loss of sight of the other, to the loss of connection with the other yet essential for one to be. It is therefore urgent that the university institution restore this dissolved articulation between the members of the university community. The university institution must recreate a link between « the individual and the common, the particular interest and the universal interest » (Grand, 2016).

The restoration of this break is all the more important as the image, credibility and prestige of the university institution in Benin seem to depend largely on the relations between teachers and learners, most often far from the major ethical values and principles at work in higher education, on the one hand, from the lack of knowledge of the meaning of education, the tensions between the values conveyed by the university institution and the personal normative referents of teachers, on the other hand. Research has shown that differences between institutional and personal values, as well as a lack of support, can help encourage inappropriate academic behaviour (Bruhn, 2008). As such, a mediation of values consisting in the creation, by the various stakeholders, of a framework for redefining the operating standards of the institution and the university community on the basis of co-shared values aimed at inducing a return to values and improving interactions between teachers and learners as well as the image and prestige of universities in Benin is necessary.

A return to ethical values is therefore essential so that the category of teachers « - reproductive agents » of their socialization with values competing with those of the higher education teaching profession can find the social benchmarks that their profession requires in order to regain the rank of their colleagues whose socialization is in line with the meaning and responsibility of the educator. These benchmarks that I have designated by the concept of a unified cultural and pedagogical basis will have to emerge from a co-construction work in order to be a basis shared by all actors.

If we have searched to understand how the shortcomings and absences that have become structural in higher education are experienced and their effects on the relations between teachers and learners and on the current image, credibility and prestige of the university institution in Benin, it is also to show that the structural constraints faced by members of the university community are also a ground that maintains such relationships and this disconnection with values. If the lack of teachers is solved from time to time by assigning several courses to a single teacher, to make him a « super-teacher », the risk of influence trafficking as a drift is also great. If it is true that the cardinal principles of ethics, which allow not only the preservation of a climate of collegiality, the acceptance of difference and criticism in mutual respect, the valorisation and recognition of the rights of others are essential to improve the image of the University as a training institution through a return to values and a greater development of its users, it is equally true that University must introduce new institutions within it to expand its role and correct the dysfunctions identified in this work.

It is clear from this work that the university institution must undergo profound transformations in terms of structuring through the introduction of new institutions.

These institutions will contribute to restoring, through better governance, trust, strengthening academic independence, and promoting a culture of transparency and responsibility within the academic institution. They will give new roles to the university institution and will contribute not only to positively reorienting the relationship between teachers and learners, but also to giving it a new and energizing aura.

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